

EXPERIMENTAL DYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF DAMAGE EVOLUTION IN SHORT FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Strain localization and failure behaviour of short glass fibre-reinforced polypropylene (SGFPP) are investigated on compact tension (CT) specimens using the Henschel Random Access Tracking system. The displacements measured in the process-zone are used to compute the transient strain fields during the entire loading process. Analysis of these results reveals reliable conclusions towards the local elastic and failure behaviour of SGFPP.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, many failure mechanisms have efficiently been described by continuum damage mechanics (CDM). Almost all damage criteria are based on threshold levels computed from the actual strains in the material, requiring very precise measurement of all strain components involved.

The experimental monitoring of fracture and damage phenomena in composite materials is an innovative research area, attracting more and more attention through an increasing interest in the failure behaviour of these materials. Not many results are practically available since the existing experimental tools were not always suited to carry out a two-dimensional local failure analysis in materials. Nevertheless, interesting contributions have been realized by Karger-Kocsis and Czigány [1-4] and Krey et al. [5]. In these experiments mainly two techniques, namely acoustic emission (AE) and light-microscopy (LM), were used to register the failure events in a fibre-reinforced composite material.

In this study the Henschel Random Access Tracking system [6] is used to identify the local failure behaviour of short glass fibre-reinforced polypropylene. Along with the registration

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Figure 1: Experimental set-up for the Hentschel strain measurement system

of the transient local deformations, global force-displacement results are obtained in a classical way.

THE HENTSCHEL RANDOM ACCESS TRACKING SYSTEM

The enhanced Random Access Tracking system from Hentschel was presented in 1990. The system is based on a digital registration of optical signals reflected by retro-reflective markers. The system, schematically represented in Fig. 1, tracks the positions of multiple points in space at high speed with a high resolution in real time mode (real time, high speed, high resolution, multi-point tracking). The sample rate can be speeded up to 7500 markers per second. The markers, made of a special retro-reflective foil, are illuminated by halogen light and scanned by a high speed window method. Each marker is traced in line search mode within a small window around the centre of the marker. Inside this window the scanning is done by a sine wave signal with a frequency of 120 kHz. These signals are captured from the camera to the video-interface for further analysis and are on-line transferred to the computer connected to the system with a DMA-interface. This on-line transfer is made possible by the windowscan technique, necessitating only a small amount of data to be transferred. The system offers a maximum resolution of 32678 by 32678 pixels within the field of view (f.o.v.). The smallest dimension of this field measures 30 by 30 millimetres in the experiments that are performed. The size of the trace windows around the markers can be adapted discretely from 0.5% (f.o.v.) to 4% (f.o.v.). The effective resolution is reduced if the window size increases because of a limited window resolution of 256 by 256 pixels.

The video-interface is designed to operate and control simultaneously two cameras, offering a full stereoscopic displacement set. Combining data of both cameras gives the deformation of each marker in a three-dimensional space. Only one camera is used for the in-plane analysis of CT-specimens. The accuracy that can be achieved with this dynamic measurement system is better than 0.1% of the f.o.v., if calibration and distortion correction are adequately performed. For the smallest CT-specimen this accuracy equals approximately 30

μm . The accuracy of dynamic measurements is enhanced by an appropriate SVD-filtering (Singular Value Decomposition) scheme and an initial precise static measurement of the undeformed state.

EXPERIMENTS ON SGFPP

THE COMPACT-TENSION TEST

The standard CT-test is a well-known standard test method for plane fracture of metals and for the measurement of fatigue crack growth rates. The test as described in the ASTM Standard E399 [7] and E647 [8] was fitted to the particular requirements imposed by composite materials [9]. The proposed testing protocol takes into account the major problems and difficulties in composites and polymers. The specimen is fixed at both the top and the bottom by a clevis and pin assembly. The specimen and loading arrangement is used for tension loading only.

The principal parameters that identify a CT-specimen are the characteristic dimension W and the notch depth a . The CT-specimens used in the current experiments were mechanically cut out of SGFPP-plates (Azdel® PD3243) with a thickness of 3.8 mm, kindly supplied by GE Plastics Europe. The characteristic dimension W of the small, medium and large specimens is 50, 75 and 100 mm, respectively. The total length of the machined notch was taken equal to 30% of W . The glass-fibre content of the SGFPP-plates was 30 wt.%, with a fibre-length of 12.5 mm. Different test conditions were realized by using three loading rates for each specimen size. These loading rates were scaled to equivalent values for the medium and large specimen, to evaluate the inherent size effect.

RESULTS

Spatial Strain Analysis

The corresponding strain fields have been computed for all tests, using a gradient deformation formulation applied on the filtered displacements. The results obtained from these computations can be graphically visualized at different time steps. A typical result is shown in Fig. 2, and gives a three-dimensional view of the Y-component of the strain (aligned with the load line) in a small CT-specimen. The computed strain field is depicted over the entire marker field covering the elastically deformed CT-specimen (shortly after the test started). The small elastic deformations in the composite specimen can be very well retrieved. Noise reduction is done efficiently, yielding a smooth acceptable strain field. Similar results are obtained for the other specimen sizes. During the entire loading process, strains are also computed in cracked material. The strains derived from the displacements over the crack region will be denoted as fictive strains. The basic idea behind this approach rises from continuum damage mechanics, where the cracks are treated continuously as fully damaged material. The numerical values computed for these fictive strains may be large, and can exceed 100% in the final failure stage. In a continuous strain field, a threshold value is assumed beyond which the computed strain can no longer be considered as physical strains. The fictive strains thus found, no longer characterize the behaviour of the continuum, but

Figure 2: E_{yy} strain field - Marker field

Figure 3: E_{yy} strain field - Small CT-specimen

a physical crack (crack opening and propagation).

The initial elastic region covers an important fraction of the marker field. The extent of this region will significantly change during the entire test, and reveals important characteristics with respect to the failure behaviour of SGFPP. The same strain field can be depicted in a plane greyscaled view (Fig. 3). To clarify the spatial implementation of the markers on the CT-specimen, the entire strain field has been embedded in its CT-configuration.

Strain Evolution and Failure Modes

The entire deformation process can be monitored by sampling the strain field in time. A specific experiment is selected for further analysis, but most of the conclusions remain valid for all tests. The experiments on medium sized specimens loaded at medium rate (15 mm/min) will be used in the subsequent analysis. The characteristic force-displacement (along the load line) curve (FD-curve) from such an experiment is shown in Fig. 4. Eight samples have been taken during the deformation process, stipulated on the FD-graph. The four first samples were taken before the maximum force was reached, whereas the subsequent four samples were taken after this maximum. The corresponding strain fields (the Y-strain component) are depicted in Fig. 5 before F_{max} is reached and in Fig. 6 after F_{max} is reached.

The steep ascending branch of the FD-curve results from the local build-up of the elastic strains and the crack initiation. The maximum strain in the zone of measurement reaches a value of approximately 10%. The global maximum strain that can be achieved in classical tensile tests on SGFPP, reaches a value of approximately 3%. This tensile strain of 3% is an underestimate of the actual strain in the localization zone. At a fictive strain level of 10% found in CT-tests, failure is initiated. Matrix deformation and fibre-matrix debonding occur before the maximum load is reached.

The conclusions with respect to the failure process become even more clear, if the strains computed at all marker locations, are represented graphically. Attention is focused on the variation of the equivalent strains in the specimen. Note, that the differences between this equivalent strain and the strain component aligned with the load line, are minor. The results can be observed in Fig. 8, along with the associated force evolution in Fig. 7.

It can be noticed in Fig. 8 that the number of observations in the 2 – 3% zone, increases

Figure 4: Force - Displacement curve

Figure 5: E_{yy} strain field evolution in a CT-specimen (W = 75 [mm])

Figure 6: E_{yy} strain field evolution in a CT-specimen ($W = 75$ [mm])

Figure 7: Force-Time curve

Figure 8: Equivalent strains

Figure 9: Fictive equivalent strains

rapidly to a maximum value, and starts decreasing at a moment shortly after the ultimate load is reached. During the initiation of failure, a large elastic deformed zone is built up, which starts to decrease when fibre-matrix debonding occurs. After 20 seconds a part of the material starts to unload, since the number of observations in the 2 – 3% zone decreases in favour of the observations in the 0–2% zone and the 3–4% zone. This phase mainly controls the crack propagation through the specimen, by which a part of the accumulated elastic energy is released in the crack. After 30 seconds the number of observations exceeding the strain level 4% stabilizes, resulting in a quasi-horizontal curve in Fig. 8. Crack propagation is slowed down, and all further deformations are mainly caused by crack opening. This phenomenon is also depicted in Fig. 9. This figure represents the strain behaviour above 4%. It can be seen that at time $t = 30s$ the number of observations in the 4 – 10% zone decreases in favour of the observations in the zone above 10%. The concerning material is submitted to a crack opening process, while crack propagation is stabilizing. In the load curve, it can be noticed that the load decrease rate reaches an extreme value.

Another interesting remark can be made regarding the threshold value, characterizing the irreversible damaging of the composite material. It can be observed from Fig. 8 that the zone with strains above 4% never reduces, implying that the threshold value is smaller than 4%. It can also be noticed that this is not the case for the 3 – 4% zone. The unknown threshold value must therefore reside between 3% and 4%. A more sensitive computation was carried out, to retrieve a better prediction of this threshold value. The strain value, above which the affected zone does not experience a size reduction has been computed. A mean value of 3.48% with a standard deviation of 0.32% was found when all tests were considered.

CONCLUSIONS

The deformation and failure process of SGFPP in a CT-test can subsequently be described by :

1. Build-up of a wide elastically deformed zone behind the notch tip. This process is mainly controlled by matrix deformation.

2. Crack initiation above a threshold value for the equivalent strain (exceeding 3%). Matrix deformation and fibre-matrix debonding characterizes this stage.
3. The load reaches the maximum value and decreases subsequently. Unloading of the elastically deformed zone in favour of crack propagation. Fibre-matrix debonding and some fibre pull-out.
4. Stabilization of the crack propagation, crack opening.

The damage process zone behind the crack tip mainly covers the elastic deformation and the crack initiation mentioned above. These different deformation stages can be identified in all tests, for all sizes and all loading rates. These conclusions regarding the fracture behaviour and the failure modes of SGFPP in the CT-test, can be compared with results obtained from AE- and LM-techniques [4]. Many conclusions following from the AE-techniques are confirmed, and additional details with respect to the failure process are retrieved.

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